

Editorial Note

Scientific Synergy for Sustainability: An Editorial Insight into GreenTech Journal's First Issue of 2025

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Dear Scientists and Researchers,

We are pleased to present you with the first issue of 2025. In this issue of *GreenTech – Journal of Green Technology and Environment*, we bring you scientific studies on environmentally friendly technologies, sustainable materials and applications aimed at minimizing environmental impacts. The original research and compilations in this issue bring together innovative approaches to sustainability in different disciplines.

The issue opens with a compilation article titled “**Green Human Resources: Strategies for a Sustainable Future**” written by Serap Kaymakçı. The article comprehensively examines the role of green human resources management in environmentally friendly institutional transformation and shows how basic human resources functions such as recruitment, training and performance evaluation can be transformed with a green vision.

In the study titled “**Comparison of Color Parameters in Lotofa, Zebrano, Sapele, Ekaba, and Ash Woods Applied with Synthetic-Based Furniture Varnish**” prepared on wood surface aesthetics and coating technologies, the effects of synthetic varnish applications on color parameters on five different wood species were meticulously examined. The research provides important contributions on how aesthetic criteria can be supported with engineering data in the furniture industry.

The article “**Air Pollution Estimation and Trends in Mainz (2017–2022): A Case Study**” by Sahar Gerandaneh et al. provides an original methodological contribution to air quality monitoring at the urban scale by presenting a comparative analysis of PM_{2.5} particulate matter concentrations with satellite and ground sensor data. The annual air pollution trends in the city of Mainz and the effects of the pandemic period are evaluated in detail in the study.

The review article titled “**Biomass Carbonization, Briquetting and Briquette Characterization: A Review**” on biomass energy and circular economy systematically addresses the conversion processes of biomass resources in fuel briquette production. Current literature on the potential of biomass resources to sustainable energy, carbonization techniques and physical properties of briquettes has been compiled and a solid basis has been established for future research.

The issue ends with the study by Fatih Tuncay Efe and colleagues titled “**Determination of Selected Surface Properties of Keranji (*Dialium indum* L.) Wood Treated with Antique and Cinnamon Natural Wood Oils**”. This article evaluates the changes in color, brightness and whiteness index of keranji wood treated with environmentally friendly natural oils, combines traditional preservation techniques with modern analyses and suggests ecological alternatives for the wood industry.

The articles in this issue are the product of a vision that supports environmental awareness with scientific data and encourages innovative and sustainable solutions. We would like to thank all our authors and referees and wish our readers an inspiring reading experience.

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